

Isolation and Identification of the Insecticide Endosulfan from Biological Materials by Thin Layer Chromatographic Technique

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Endosulfan (Thiodan), an organochloro insecticide, is widely used in agriculture. It is highly toxic to human and warm blooded animals¹. The active ingredient of endosulfan is 6,7,8,9,10,10-hexachloro-1,5,5a,6,9,9a-hexahydro-6,9-metheno-2,4,3-benzodioxathiepin-3-oxide². The stereoisomers of

the active ingredient are known: α -endosulfan and β -endosulfan³. The compounds differ significantly in physicochemical and toxic properties⁴. The metabolism pathways of endosulfan^{4,5} are shown in Scheme 1.

Results and Discussion

Different R_f values and solvent systems used for the separation and identifications of endosulfan from different autopsy tissues are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Two spots are obtained indicating the presence of both α - and β -isomers in the sample. The development of intense blue colour spots by visualisa-

tion test-(b), a selective spray reagent for endosulfan, may be explained in the following manner.

By spraying the spots with NaOH solution⁶ followed by cobalt acetate solution, yellowish brown

TABLE 1—SOLVENT SYSTEMS FOR THE TLC SEPARATION OF ENDOSULFAN

Sl. no.	Solvent system	Ratio (v/v)
1.	Petroleum ether : Liquid paraffin	90 : 10
2.	n-Hexane : Acetone	95 : 5
3.	Cyclohexane : Liquid paraffin	85 : 15
4.	Cyclohexane : Dichloromethane	90 : 10
5.	Cyclohexane : Chloroform	80 : 20
6.	Petroleum ether	100

TABLE 2— R_f VALUES OF ENDOSULFAN IN DIFFERENT SOLVENT SYSTEMS ON SILICA-GEL G PLATE

Material	100 R_f in various solvent systems*					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Endosulfan	29.44	30.66	17.57	23.60	13.50	18.93
Tissue extracts	29.44	30.66	17.57	23.60	13.50	18.93

*Refer to the solvent systems as of Sl. nos. in Table 1.

spots of tetravalent cobalt appeared after five min. On treatment with *o*-toluidine in acetic acid, the spots changed to intense blue colour due to quinoidal oxidation product of the former⁷, which is stable for about 30.0 min in the latter medium and slowly faded away. Other organochloro insecticides such as endrin, aldrin, dieldrin, DDT and BHC did not respond to this colorimetric spot test. Moreover, constituents of viscera, such as amino acids, peptides, proteins etc, but generally co-extracted with the insecticides, did not interfere⁸ in the process. The reagent is more sensitive than ethanolic diphenylamine⁹, *o*-toluidine, *o*-dianisidine and upon exposure to uv-light¹⁰. As such, in the absence of any specific chemical test for endosulfan, the tlc technique with specific spray reagent is quite diagnostic for endosulfan.

The present investigation explores that tlc technique and chromogenic tests can be applied successfully for identification and semiquantitative determination of endosulfan in biological materials in forensic toxicological work as well as in warm blooded animals like rats injected with the insecticide for behavioural study. Application of above techniques may be a new insight to the field of toxicology.

Experimental

Two different techniques were employed for extracting the compound from visceral matters.

The macerated tissues (25 g) were mixed with equal amount of anhydrous sodium sulphate and chloroform (50 ml) and refluxed on a hot water-bath for 1 h. After cooling, the chloroform layer was separated and treated with concentrated H₂SO₄ and kept overnight. The chloroform layer was then neutralised with 10% NaOH and washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and evaporated to dryness.

The homogenised viscera (20 g) was extracted with ether (2×20 ml) at pH 5 and with 2*N* HCl¹¹.

The combined ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, concentrated and evaporated to dryness.

Procedure: Glass plates (20 cm×10 cm) were coated with 0.25 mm thickness of silica gel G (Merck), air-dried, activated at 110° for 30 minutes and cooled. Samples were dissolved in methanol and the plates were spotted with the extracts along with the control technical endosulfan (Hindustan Insecticides Limited) and developed for 30 min. Different solvent systems were used in order to obtain a good separation. The solvent systems found to give satisfactory separation as shown by the R_f values¹², are shown in Tables 1, 2.

Spray reagents: When the solvent travelled 10.0 cm from the base line, the plates were removed from the solvent chamber and air-dried for about 10.0 min. Following spray reagents were used for detection: (a) 1.0% ethanolic diphenylamine solution⁹ was sprayed over the plate and was exposed to sunlight/uv-light for 15.0 min resulting green coloured spots, and (b) the plate was sprayed with 5.0% NaOH solution in 5.0% cobalt acetate solution followed by 1.0% *o*-toluidine⁷ in acetic acid developing intense blue coloured spots. The R_f values and the characteristic coloured spots were well compared with that of the control.

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